

**AN APPROXIMATE ANALYTICAL SOLUTION FOR
INTERLAMINAR STRESSES IN ANGLE-PLY LAMINATES**

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ABSTRACT

An improved approximate analytical solution for interlaminar stresses in finite width, symmetric, angle-ply laminated coupons subjected to axial loading is presented. The solution is based upon statically admissible stress fields which take into consideration local property mismatch effects and global equilibrium requirements. Unknown constants in the admissible stress states are determined through minimization of the complementary energy. Typical results are presented for through-the-thickness and interlaminar stress distributions for angle-ply laminates. It is shown that the results represent an improved approximate analytical solution for interlaminar stresses.

KEYWORDS: Interlaminar Shear Stresses; Composites; Analytical Solution; Angle-Ply Laminates; Coefficient of Mutual Influence Mismatch; Complementary Energy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The existence of interlaminar stresses is an important problem in both the theory and application of laminated composites. Because of the potentially catastrophic consequences of interlaminar stresses, the problem has been studied continuously since the original works of Bogy (1968), Puppo and Evensen (1970) and Pipes and Pagano (1970). A variety of solutions is now available; however, they are primarily numerical in nature and therefore of limited applicability for thick laminates and general purpose optimization studies. With the current strong desire to use thick laminates and the need for optimization procedures in the design of all types of laminates, completely general, efficient solutions for interlaminar stresses are more necessary than ever.

An approximate analytical solution recently presented by Kassapoglou and Lagace (1986) represents an important step toward providing a simple, efficient method for predicting interlaminar stresses. The method works quite well for many, but unfortunately, not all laminates. Since the Kassapoglou and Lagace solution (herein after referred to as the KL solution) is based entirely on global equilibrium considerations, it does not produce accurate results near interfaces where local mismatch of properties is present, but interlaminar stresses are not required to satisfy global equilibrium.

The method presented in this paper represents an extension of the KL solution to include additional terms in the assumed stress field. The additional terms are associated with the local material property mismatch in coefficient

of mutual influence between adjacent layers.

The accuracy of the method is demonstrated through comparison of interlaminar shear stress results with the KL solution and finite element results for angle-ply laminates.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problem under consideration is depicted in Fig. 1. A long, finite width, symmetric laminate is subjected to uniaxial loading. A global coordinate system (x_1, x_2, x_3) is established as indicated in the figure. Local coordinates $(x, y, z^{(k)})$ are established within each layer where $y = b - x_2$ is measured from the free edge and $z^{(k)}$ of the k th layer is measured from the bottom of the layer. Away from the ends where axial load is applied, all stresses and strains are independent of the axial coordinate. The plate is assumed to be sufficiently wide that classical lamination theory stresses are recovered at the center of the plate. Individual layers of the laminate are assumed to be homogeneous, orthotropic (off-axis) elastic materials.

Fig. 1. Laminate Configuration

The constitutive equation of each layer may be written in the form

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{33} \\ 2\epsilon_{23} \\ 2\epsilon_{13} \\ 2\epsilon_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} & 0 & 0 & S_{16} \\ & S_{22} & S_{23} & 0 & 0 & S_{26} \\ & & S_{33} & 0 & 0 & S_{36} \\ & \text{SYM} & & S_{44} & S_{45} & 0 \\ & & & & S_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where S_{ij} is the transformed compliance matrix. It is known from the previous works that a three dimensional state of stress exists in a boundary layer region along the free edge of the laminate. Further, for the idealized problem of distinct layers of linear elastic materials, the interlaminar normal stress, σ_{33} , and interlaminar shear stress, σ_{13} , can be singular at the free edge for some laminate stacking sequences.

3. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The mathematical formulation of the present solution follows that of the KL solution with the exception that additional terms are added to the assumed stress distributions to account for local mismatch in the coefficient of mutual influence, ($\eta_{xy,x} \equiv 2\epsilon_{12}/\epsilon_{11}$), between adjacent layers. Separation of variables for y and z dependence leads to a general functional form for the stresses $\sigma_{ij}^{(k)}$ in the k th layer.

$$\sigma_{ij}^{(k)} = f_{ij}^{(k)}(y)g_{ij}^{(k)}(z) + h_{ij}^{(k)}(y)l_{ij}^{(k)}(z) \quad i = 1,2,3, \quad j = 2,3 \quad (2)$$

This functional form is a combination of two effects:

a) global equilibrium

$$\sigma_{ij(\text{g})} = f_{ij}^{(k)}(y)g_{ij}^{(k)}(z) \quad i = 1,2,3, \quad j = 2,3 \quad (3)$$

b) mismatch in coefficient of mutual influence

$$\sigma_{ij(\text{m})} = h_{ij}^{(k)}(y)l_{ij}^{(k)}(z) \quad i = 1, \quad j = 2,3 \quad (4)$$

3.1. Global Equilibrium Following the KL solution, the final form of the statically admissible stress state satisfying global equilibrium is

$$\sigma_{22}^{(k)} = \bar{\sigma}_{22}^{(k)} \left[1 - \frac{\lambda}{\lambda-1} \left(e^{-\phi y} - \frac{1}{\lambda} e^{-\lambda \phi y} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{33}^{(k)} = \phi^2 \frac{\lambda}{\lambda-1} \left[\lambda e^{-\lambda \phi y} - e^{-\phi y} \right] \left[\bar{\sigma}_{22}^{(k)} \frac{z^2}{2} + B_4^{(k)} z + B_5^{(k)} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{23}^{(k)} = \phi \frac{\lambda}{\lambda-1} \left[e^{-\phi y} - e^{-\lambda \phi y} \right] \left[\bar{\sigma}_{22}^{(k)} z + B_4^{(k)} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_{13}^{(k)} = \phi e^{-\phi y} (\bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)} z + B_2^{(k)}) \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_{12}^{(k)} = \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)} (1 - e^{-\phi y}) \quad (9)$$

where

$$B_2^{(k)} = \sum_{j=k+1}^n \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(j)} t^{(j)} \quad (10)$$

$$B_4^{(k)} = \sum_{j=k+1}^n \bar{\sigma}_{22}^{(j)} t^{(j)} \quad (11)$$

$$B_5^{(k)} = \sum_{j=k+1}^n t^{(j)} \bar{\sigma}_{22}^{(j)} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} t^{(j)} + \sum_{m=k+1}^{j-1} t^{(m)} \right\} \quad (12)$$

ϕ and λ are unknown constants to be determined, and \sim denotes classical lamination theory (CLT) stresses. It is noted that stress continuity between plies requires that ϕ and λ be constant throughout the laminate.

The axial stresses $\sigma_{11}^{(k)}$ in each ply are determined from Hooke's Law and the strain-displacement expressions. This results in the equation

$$\sigma_{11}^{(k)} = \frac{1}{S_{11}^{(k)}} \left[\left\{ S_{11}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{11}^{(k)} + S_{12}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{22}^{(k)} + S_{16}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)} \right\} - \left\{ S_{12}^{(k)} \sigma_{22}^{(k)} + S_{13}^{(k)} \sigma_{33}^{(k)} + S_{16}^{(k)} \sigma_{12}^{(k)} \right\} \right] \quad (13)$$

These stress distributions satisfy pointwise and global equilibrium, stress free boundary conditions, interfacial traction continuity conditions, and CLT stress states away from the free edges.

3.2. Mismatch in Coefficient of Mutual Influence The goal of this paper is to provide accurate interlaminar shear stress distributions for angle-ply laminates. This is accomplished by adding terms associated with the mismatch in coefficient of mutual influence at interfaces between adjacent layers to the KL solution. As indicated in equation 4, these contributions are assumed non-zero only for the σ_{13} and σ_{12} stress components. The function $I_{13}^{(k)}(z)$ is chosen to be quadratic in z and to decay away from an interface. The $h_{13}^{(k)}(y)$ functions are chosen such that the stress contributions resulting from mismatch are self-equilibrating. Thus, the mismatch effects permit the existence of additional non-zero stress contributions, but they do not alter the global force and moment equilibrium established through the $f_{ij}^{(k)}(y)$ and $g_{ij}^{(k)}(z)$ functions.

The non-zero stress components associated with the mismatch in coefficient of mutual influence are assumed to be proportional to the mismatches in $\eta_{xy,x}$ at the two interfaces bounding the ply of interest. The proportionality constant is taken to be the product of the shear modulus of the matrix, G , times the applied axial strain, ϵ_x . The mismatches in coefficient of mutual influence at the two interfaces bounding the k th layer are defined

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\eta_{xy}(k,1) &= \eta_{xy,x}(k-1) - \eta_{xy,x}(k) \\ \delta\eta_{xy}(k,2) &= \eta_{xy,x}(k) - \eta_{xy,x}(k+1)\end{aligned}\quad (14)$$

with $\delta\eta(1,1) = \delta\eta(N,2) \equiv 0$

where the layers above and below the k th layer are designated $k-1$ and $k+1$, respectively (Fig. 1).

The stresses in a generic layer are influenced by mismatch effects from the two adjoining interfaces, therefore the through-the-thickness function $I_{13}^{(k)}$ is assumed to have the form

$$I_{13}^{(k)}(z) = \left[\delta\eta_{xy}(k,1)z^2/t^2 + \delta\eta_{xy}(k,2)(1-z/t)^2 \right] G\epsilon_x \quad (15)$$

Equilibrium then requires that the function $I_{12}^{(k)}$ have the form

$$I_{12}^{(k)}(z) = \frac{dI_{13}^{(k)}}{dz}(z) = \left\{ \frac{2z}{t^2} \left[\delta\eta_{xy}(k,1) + \delta\eta_{xy}(k,2) \right] - \frac{2}{t} \delta\eta_{xy}(k,2) \right\} G\epsilon_x \quad (16)$$

The associated function $h_{13}^{(k)}(y)$ is chosen to have the self-equilibrating form

$$h_{13}^{(k)}(y) = \lambda e^{-\lambda\phi y} - e^{-\phi y} \quad (17)$$

If follows from equilibrium that $h_{12}^{(k)}$ must have the form

$$h_{12}^{(k)}(y) = \int h_{13}(y) dy = \frac{1}{\phi} \left[-c^{-\lambda\phi y} + c^{-\phi y} \right] + A_6 \quad (18)$$

where the constant of integration, A_6 , must be zero to satisfy the free edge boundary condition $\sigma_{12} = 0$ at $y = 0$. The non-zero stress contributions associated with mismatch in coefficient of mutual influence are then

$$\sigma_{13}^{(k)}(\delta\eta) = G\epsilon_x (\lambda c^{-\lambda\phi y} - c^{-\phi y}) \left[\delta\eta_{xy}(k, 1) \frac{z^2}{t^2} + \delta\eta_{xy}(k, 2) \left(1 - \frac{z}{t}\right)^2 \right] \quad (19)$$

$$\sigma_{12}^{(k)}(\delta\eta) = \frac{-G\epsilon_x}{\phi} (c^{-\lambda\phi y} - c^{-\phi y}) \left[\frac{2z}{t^2} \left[\delta\eta_{xy}(k, 1) + \delta\eta_{xy}(k, 2) \right] - \frac{2}{t} \delta\eta_{xy}(k, 2) \right] \quad (20)$$

These stresses satisfy the free edge boundary condition on σ_{12} and do not disturb the CLT values at $y=b$. Also, traction continuity between layers is satisfied by these forms.

The final form for the assumed stresses is given by the sum of equations 5-10, 19 and 20. These assumed stress states are statically admissible. The unknown constants ϕ and λ are determined through minimization of the complementary energy.

3.3. Complementary Energy The complementary energy Π_c can be expressed as a summation over the individual plies as

$$\Pi_c = \sum_{k=1}^n \Pi_c^{(k)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{2} \iint_{V^{(k)}} [\sigma]^T [S]^{(k)} [\sigma] dv - \iint_{S_u} \{T\}^T \{\bar{u}\} dA \quad (21)$$

where $\{\bar{u}\}$ are the prescribed displacements and $\{T\}^T$ are the associated tractions on the displacement boundary, S_u . The stationary value of Π_c corresponds to the conditions

$$\frac{\partial \Pi_c}{\partial \lambda} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial \Pi_c}{\partial \phi} = 0 \quad (22)$$

These conditions can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \Pi_c}{\partial \phi} &= \phi^4 \{d_2(\lambda^5 + 2\lambda^4 + \lambda^3)\} \\
 &+ \phi^2 \{-d_7\lambda^6 + \lambda^5 [3d_1 + 4d_3 + d_7] + \lambda^4 [6d_1 + 8d_3 + d_7] \\
 &+ \lambda^3 [3d_1 + 4d_3 - d_7]\} + \phi \{\lambda^5 [-4d_4 - 8d_8] + \lambda^4 [-8d_4 - 8d_8] \\
 &+ \lambda^3 [4d_4 + 8d_8] + \lambda^2 [8d_4 + 8d_8]\} + \{3d_5[-\lambda^5 + \lambda^4 + \lambda^3 - \lambda^2]\} = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{d\Pi_c}{d\lambda} &= \lambda^7 \{d_7\phi^2\} + \lambda^6 \{3d_7\phi^2\} + \lambda^5 \{4d_6\phi^3 - d_7\phi^2 + 4d_8\phi + 3d_5\} \\
 &+ \lambda^4 \{4d_6\phi^3 - 3d_7\phi^2 + \phi[8d_4 + 12d_8] + d_5\} + \lambda^3 \{\phi[12d_4 + 12d_8] - 3d_5\} \\
 &+ \lambda^2 \{\phi[4d_4 + 4d_8] - d_5\} = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_1 &= \sum_{k=1}^n \left[S_{66}^{(k)} - \frac{[S_{16}^{(k)}]^2}{S_{11}^{(k)}} \right] [\bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)}]^2 t(k) \\
 d_2 &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n S_{33}^{(k)} \left[[\bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)}]^2 t^3(k) + 3B_2^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)} t^2(k) + 3[B_2^{(k)}]^2 t(k) \right] \\
 d_3 &= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{S_{16}^{(k)}}{S_{11}^{(k)}} \left[S_{11}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{11}^{(k)} + S_{12}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{22}^{(k)} + S_{16}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)} \right] \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)} t(k) \\
 d_4 &= \sum_{k=1}^n \left[S_{66}^{(k)} - \frac{[S_{16}^{(k)}]^2}{S_{11}^{(k)}} \right] \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_x [\delta\eta(k, 1) - \delta\eta(k, 2)] \\
 d_5 &= \frac{4}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n \left[S_{66}^{(k)} \frac{\bar{\sigma}_x^2}{t(k)} [\delta\eta^2(k, 2) - \delta\eta(k, 1)\delta\eta(k, 2) + \delta\eta^2(k, 1)] \right] \\
 d_6 &= \frac{1}{12} \sum_{k=1}^n [S_{33}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_x \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)} [t^2(k) [\delta\eta(k, 2) + 3\delta\eta(k, 1)] + 4B_2(k) t(k) [\delta\eta(k, 1) + \delta\eta(k, 2)]] \\
 d_7 &= \frac{1}{15} \sum_{k=1}^n [S_{33}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_x^2 t(k) [3\delta\eta^2(k, 1) + \delta\eta(k, 1)\delta\eta(k, 2) + 3\delta\eta^2(k, 2)]] \\
 d_8 &= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{S_{16}^{(k)}}{S_{11}^{(k)}} [S_{11}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{11}^{(k)} + S_{12}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{22}^{(k)} + S_{16}^{(k)} \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(k)}] \bar{\sigma}_x [\delta\eta(k, 1) - \delta\eta(k, 2)]
 \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

and $\bar{\sigma}_x = G\epsilon_x$.

The d_i terms are functions of the laminate material properties and stacking sequence; thus they are laminate dependent.

Equation 23 is 4th order in ϕ and eqn. 24 is 7th order in λ . The roots of these equations were obtained using the IMSL routine DZPLRC. Of the 28 possible pairs of roots, the pair with real and positive ϕ and λ corresponding to the minimum value of the complementary energy was taken as the correct pair.

It is noted that the final equations for the stress distributions and equations (23) and (24) are for a generic, symmetric angle-ply laminate subjected to axial strain. For a specific fiber orientation and stacking sequence, the coefficients d_i must be determined and the 4th and 7th order equations then solved for ϕ and λ . With ϕ and λ known, stress values can be determined at any location $y, z^{(k)}$.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results are presented for graphite-epoxy angle-ply laminates in the form of stress distributions through-the-thickness (at the free edge) and along layer interfaces. Comparisons are presented for results based upon the present modified solution, the KL solution and finite element results generated by the authors using a previously developed program. The axial strain loading was $\epsilon_x = 0.1\%$. The ply thickness was 0.158 mm and $b/H = 12.5$. The graphite-epoxy material properties used are given in Table 1.

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{23}	matrix G (GPa)
132.4	10.8	0.23	5.7	0.49	1.7

As shown in the following figures, the modified solution provides very good predictions of the interlaminar stresses when compared with the finite element results. When studying the figures it should be borne in mind that the magnitude of the stresses at the intersection of layer interfaces and the free edge (the singular point) as predicted by a displacement based finite element formulation are a function of the size of the finite elements near this point (Herakovich, et al, 1985). Thus undue reliance should not be given to the magnitudes at these singular points. As will be apparent, the modified solution provides improved results as compared with the KL solution primarily at those interfaces where global equilibrium is satisfied identically by the lamination theory stresses, but local mismatch in material properties requires the existence of nonzero interlaminar stresses.

Fig. 2. Through-the-Thickness σ_{13} Comparisons

The results in Fig. 2a for a $[10_2/-10_2]_s$ laminate show that there is reasonably good correlation between all three solutions for this laminate. Similar results were obtained for other "clustered" angle-ply laminates with stacking sequence of the type $[\theta_2/-\theta_2]_s$. For the $[\theta_2/-\theta_2]_s$ laminates global equilibrium requires that the interlaminar shear stress σ_{13} be non-zero throughout the thickness of the laminates.

In contrast to the results for clustered laminates, the results in Fig. 2b for an "alternating" $[(\pm 10)_2]_s$ angle-ply laminate show that there are substantial differences in the predictions depending upon the method used. At the $-10/10$ (second) interface the modified solution of the present study and the finite element results predict non-zero σ_{13} of substantial magnitude whereas the KL solution predicts identically zero σ_{13} .

For the $[(\pm\theta)_2]_s$ laminates global equilibrium is satisfied at the second interface by the lamination theory stresses. Thus interlaminar stresses are not required for global equilibrium. However, for some fiber orientations, there is a large local mismatch in $\eta_{xy,x}$ at this $-\theta/\theta$ interface. This mismatch in $\eta_{xy,x}$ gives rise to locally high interlaminar shear stresses σ_{13} . The present solution predicts these stresses very accurately when compared to the finite element results. Because the KL solution is based entirely on global equilibrium, it predicts σ_{13} to be identically zero at this interface. Further, since the KL solution is linear in z there is substantial difference in the through-the-thickness distribution of σ_{13} in adjacent layers.

Fig. 3. Equilibrium and Mismatch Contributions to σ_{13}

The results in Fig. 2 also show that σ_{13} is large at $+10^\circ/-10^\circ$ interfaces. This is true because $\delta\eta_{xy}$ is large for $\theta = 10^\circ$. The shear stress decreases for larger fiber angles as the mismatch in $\eta_{xy,x}$ decreases. In view of the fact that these interlaminar shear stresses can be quite large, it is important that they be predicted accurately. This is particularly true for optimization studies and prediction of failure for combined stress states.

The contributions of various physical effects for this problem are depicted in Figs. 3a and 3b. These figures show the through the thickness distributions of σ_{13} for $[10_2/-10_2]_s$ and $[(\pm 10)_2]_s$ laminates, separated into the contributions of equilibrium effects and mismatch effects. It is clear from Fig. 3a that there is no contribution due to mismatch in the first and fourth layers of the $[10_2/-10_2]_s$ laminate whereas equilibrium contributes throughout the laminate. In contrast, both equilibrium and mismatch contribute in all layers of the $[(\pm 10)_2]_s$ laminate (Fig. 3b). The equilibrium contribution is linear through-the-thickness of the laminate whereas the mismatch contribution is nonlinear. The through-the-thickness distributions within a layer are a direct consequence of the form of the assumed stress state.

Interlaminar distributions of σ_{13} along interfaces in $[(\pm 10)_2]_s$ laminates are presented in Figs. 4-6. Figures 4 and 5 show the predictions of the present solution, the KL solution and finite element analysis along the first and second interfaces of the laminate. It is evident from the results that all three methods compare quite well at the first interface (Fig. 4), but that only the present solution and the finite element results are in agreement along the second interface (Fig. 5). The KL solution predicts zero shear stress σ_{13} along the entire interface.

Fig. 4. Comparisons for σ_{13} along +10/-10 (first) Interface.

Fig. 5. Comparisons for σ_{13} along -10/+10 (second) Interface.

The results in Fig. 6 show the total and individual contributions to the shear stress resulting from equilibrium and mismatch effects along the first interface. The results indicate that the mismatch effects are larger than the equilibrium effects at the free edge. However, the boundary layer width is approximately the same for both effects. For the second interface, the total stresses are due to mismatch effects (Fig. 5).

Fig. 6. Equilibrium and Mismatch Contributions to σ_{13} along $+10/-10$ (first) Interface.

The results in Figs. 7a and 7b show the variation in ϕ and λ as a function of fiber orientation for clustered and alternating stacking sequences. It is apparent that both parameters vary over a large range as the fiber orientation is changed. The differences in ϕ and λ for the two stacking sequences are less severe. Extremal values occur at $\theta = 30^\circ$ for ϕ and $\theta = 25^\circ$ for λ . These results are, of course, material dependent.

Fig. 7. ϕ and λ vs θ for Angle-ply Laminates

5. CONCLUSIONS

An improved approximate analytical solution for interlaminar stresses in symmetric angle-ply laminates subjected to axial loading has been presented. It has been shown that the solution provides more accurate predictions for the interlaminar shear stresses than previous analytical solutions. Further the effects of global equilibrium and local mismatch on the interlaminar stresses have been clearly delineated. Because of its analytical formulation the solution is well suited for optimization studies and investigations of interlaminar stress in laminates with many layers.

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